

METHOD OF EXPRESSING OHM'S LAW EQUATION WRITTEN IN DIFFERENTIAL FORM BY MAXWELL

Mukhammadjon Turgunovich Xalilov

Professor, Andijan machine-building institute, Uzbekistan

Alimardon Sulonovich Kholikov

Assistant, Andijan machine-building institute, Uzbekistan

Abstract: In the study of the constant current laws, the dependence of the current on the voltage for a part of the circuit and for the complete circuit is studied using Ohm's law. Using this law, it is possible to determine the volt-ampere characteristic of the conductor and the consumer. If the parameters of the conductor are given, the current passing through the circuit of the conductor allows to draw a conclusion about the current density, but to determine the current density depending on the electric field, it is necessary to use the differential form of Ohm's law. Accordingly, in this work, the methods of expressing the differential form of Ohm's law are explained.

Key words: Current strength, current density, voltage, electric resistance, relative electric conductivity, electric field, some potentials, charged particles.

Intraduction

It is known that when current flows through electric circuits, the interdependent change of current strength and voltage passing through the conductor is determined using the integral form of Ohm's law. Electric current is created by the movement of free charged particles. Given the strength of the electric field applied to the circuit and given the relative electrical conductivity or relative electrical resistance of the conductor, in addition, the flow of charged particles creates a magnetic field along with the generation of current. It is more effective to determine using the equations in the interpretation [1-4].

Method

If there is a potential difference between two arbitrary points of the conductor, then it is confirmed that there is an electric field moving electric charges between the two points of the conductor. The potential difference between points in it is equal to the work force required to move charges from one point to another [5].

To form the differential form of Ohm's law, we apply Ohm's law written in integral form to an infinitesimal cylindrical conductor [6].

Figure 1. Conductor.

Let's say that $\Delta I = j_t \Delta S$ current flows through the axis of this cylinder, where ΔS is the cross-sectional surface of the cylinder, and j_t is the current density passing along the axis of the cylinder [7].

Since the cylinder we see is infinitely small, the electric field $\vec{E}$ inside it can be taken as constant. Then the potential difference between the bases of the cylinder is equal to;

$$\Delta\varphi = E_t \Delta\ell$$

where E_t is the projection along the base of the electric field strength vector $\vec{E}$. The potential difference is measured in volts, and the electric field strength vector is measured in volts divided by meters [V/m]. Thus, Ohm's law can be written as follows for the considered infinitesimal cylinder:

$$\Delta\varphi = \Delta IR = j_t R \Delta S \quad (1)$$

where R is the resistance of the considered cylinder, the relative resistance of the conductor is the inverse expression $\frac{1}{\rho}$ is called the relative conductivity of the conductor σ -, its unit is $[\sigma]$, $\frac{1}{\text{Om} \cdot \text{m}}$;

Using this, the resistance of the cylinder ΔR is written as:

$$R = \frac{1}{\sigma} \cdot \frac{\Delta \ell}{\Delta S} \quad (2)$$

then, putting expression (2) into equation (1), we get the following:

$$j_t = \sigma E_t \quad (3)$$

Since the axis of the cylinder is taken as arbitrary, equation (3) is also true for projections of vectors $\vec{j}$ and $\vec{E}$ in arbitrary directions.

So, then we write (3) as follows:

$$\vec{j} = \sigma \vec{E} \quad (4)$$

This expression is called the differential form of Ohm's law, this equation is also called the complement of Maxwell's system of equations written for electromagnetic fields [8-10].

If we pay attention to this equation, there is no derivative in this equation, even so, the reason why this equation is called differential is that all quantities included in this equation represent one point of the field.

The second way to state the differential form of Ohm's law. Ohm's law for a part of the circuit is based on experiments by the German physicist Ohm (1787-1854), who found that the current passing through a homogeneous metal conductor is directly proportional to the voltage applied to the conductor:

$$I = \frac{U}{R} \quad (5)$$

where R is the electrical resistance of the conductor, the above equation is called Ohm blood written for a part of the circuit. That is, the current in the

conductor is directly proportional to the voltage drop across the conductor, and inversely proportional to its resistance [10-12].

The quantity G in this equation is called electrical conductivity, and its unit is measured in siemens (Cm).

$$G = \frac{1}{R}$$

It is known that the resistance of the conductor depends on the size, shape and material of the conductor. The resistance of cylindrical conductors is directly proportional to the length ℓ of the conductor and inversely proportional to the cross-sectional area of the conductor S :

$$R = \rho \frac{\ell}{S} \quad (6)$$

ρ is the coefficient, depending on the material of the conductor, it is also called the relative electrical resistance. Its unity

$$\rho, [Om \cdot m]$$

The differential form of Ohm's law can be derived as follows. For this, we put (6) into equation (5) and get the following equation:

$$I = \frac{U}{R} = \frac{U}{\rho \frac{\ell}{S}} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{U \cdot S}{\ell} \text{ yoki } \frac{I}{S} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{U}{\ell} \quad (7)$$

σ in this equation is called the relative electrical conductivity of the conductor, and its unit is expressed in siemens/meter, [Cm/m].

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\rho}$$

The expression $\frac{U}{\ell} = E$ equation (7) is called the intensity vector of the electric field in the conductor.

$$\frac{I}{S} = j$$

Denoting current density on the surface, equation (7) can be written as follows:

$$j = \sigma E \quad (8)$$

The charge carriers in the conductor are directed at each point in a direction $\vec{E}$, where the directions of $\vec{j}$ and $\vec{E}$ coincide. Therefore, equation (4) can be written in the following form.

$$j = \sigma \vec{E} \quad (9)$$

This equation is called the differential form of Ohm's law as written by Maxwell. It can be seen from this equation that the current density is directly proportional to the electric field strength vector at a given point [1, 2].

Conclusion

If students are taught the above methods of expressing Ohm's law for a part of a circuit, the calculations of the electrical circuits of the students will be simplified. He will acquire important skills in understanding the nature of the processes of the movement of charges and the formation of a current in a conductor, as well as in practical application.

REFERENCE

1. Юсупова, У. А., & Юсупов, А. Х. (2022). ЎЗГАРМАС ТОК ҚОНУНЛАРИ БЎЛИМИНИ ЎҚИТИЛИШИДА НАМОЙИШ ТАЖРИБАСИНИНГ ЎРНИ. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 17(1), 210–214.
2. Xalilov, M. T., & Yusupov, A. K. (2022). THE METHOD OF EXPRESSING MAXWELL'S EQUATIONS IN AN ORGANIC SERIES ACCORDING TO THE RULES, LAWS AND EXPERIMENTS IN THE DEPARTMENT OF ELECTROMAGNETISM. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(10), 09–15.
3. Khamidillaevich, Y. A. & others. (2019). *Problems of Introduction of Innovative Technologies and Modern Equipment in the Fishing Industry*.

4. Olimov, L. O., & Yusupov, A. K. (2021a). TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF TRANSISTOR CHARACTERISTICS OF ELECTRIC SIGNAL AMPLIFICATION IN OPTOELECTRONIC DEVICES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, 8, 169–171.

5. Olimov, L. O., & Yusupov, A. K. (2021b). The Influence Of Semiconductor Leds On The Aquatic Environment And The Problems Of Developing Lighting Devices For Fish Industry Based On Them. *The American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 3(02), 119–125.

6. Olimov, L. O., & Yusupov, A. K. (2022). DETERMINATION OF EFFICIENT OPTICAL SOURCES OF AIR PROPAGATION FOR FISHERIES BIOPHYSICAL DEVICES. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(10), 1–8.

7. Olimov, L., Yusupov, A., & Alizhanov, D. (2019). INNOVATIVE FISH FARMING DEVICE. *SCIENCE AND INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT*, 2(6), 103–107.

8. Olimov Lutfiddin Omanovich, Y. (2020). Problems Of Implementation Of Semiconductored Leds For Fishery Lighting Devices. *The American Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 189–196.

9. Omanovich, O. L., Khamidovich, A. A., & Khamidillaevich, Y. A. (2022). *Scheme of high voltage generation using semiconductor transistors*.

10. Khamidillaevich, Y. A. (2023). PARAMETERS OF OPTOELECTRONIC RADIATORS AND SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS IN DIFFERENT ENVIRONMENTS. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 2(4), 81-86.

11. Халилов, М. Т., & Юсупов, А. Х. (2023). МАКСВЕЛЛНИНГ УЗЛУКСИЗЛИК ТЕНГЛАМАСИНИНГ БАЁН ҚИЛИШ УСУЛИ. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 2(4), 77-80.

12. Yusupov, A. K. (2021). Creating a biophysical trapping device based on an optical radiation source with a light-emitting diode. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 1530–1536.